

MLIoT: Transparent and Secure ML Offloading in the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum

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Abstract—As IoT devices and robotic systems increasingly rely on ML inference, resource constraints pose a challenge for real-time execution. Efficient offloading mechanisms that leverage edge and cloud computing are essential to enable scalable, low-latency inference.

We build a novel framework that addresses three key challenges in the Cloud-Edge-IoT space: (a) secure device onboarding and OTA updates for microcontrollers, (b) cloud-native integration of microcontrollers, (c) flexible compute-intensive application offloading for ESP32-based devices to neighboring nodes with increased compute capacity.

In this paper, we present the motivation for this framework, evaluating common ML inference workloads on ESP32-based devices, low-end edge boards (Raspberry Pi), high-end edge boards (Jetson AGX) and generic cloud servers (x86). We show that offloading ML workloads to heterogeneous hardware across the Cloud-edge-IoT continuum is potentially beneficial, depending on user-defined parameters such as real-time response requirements or power budgets. Additionally, our approach enables pure cloud-native IoT device repurposing, leveraging DICE and EATs for secure device onboarding and secure OTA updates.

Index Terms—IoT, Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, acceleration, OTA updates, firmware management, kubernetes, cloud-native

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of IoT devices across domains such as smart cities, industrial automation, healthcare, and robotics has led to an increasing demand for distributed machine learning (ML) inference across diverse computing environments. Many IoT applications rely on ML models to process sensor data, detect anomalies, and make real-time decisions [1]. However, executing these models directly on resource-constrained devices is often impractical due to their limited processing power, memory, and energy constraints [2].

As a result, offloading ML inference to more capable devices in the cloud-edge-IoT continuum has emerged as a promising solution [3]–[5]. By leveraging neighboring nodes—such as edge servers, GPUs, or cloud instances—IoT devices can benefit from reduced latency, improved performance, and energy efficiency. However, existing ML offloading approaches face three major challenges:

- *Cloud-Native Microcontroller Integration*: How can microcontrollers, which typically lack native support for cloud-based orchestration, be seamlessly integrated into modern cloud environments?

- *Security and Trust*: How can IoT devices be securely onboarded in such environments and how can they securely delegate ML inference to external nodes without compromising data integrity and confidentiality?
- *Flexible Offloading Mechanisms*: How can devices dynamically decide where to offload ML workloads based on performance, latency, and energy constraints?

To address these challenges, we propose MLIoT, a framework that enables secure and transparent ML inference offloading across heterogeneous devices. Our approach is based on the following three pillars: (a) *Security through DICE [6] and EATs [7]*: We integrate DICE and EATs to ensure trusted device onboarding and firmware integrity verification; (b) *Cloud-Native Offloading via vAccel [8]*: We extend the vAccel framework, a cloud-native API remoting system, to support transparent workload delegation from microcontrollers (e.g., ESP32) to edge and cloud resources; (c) *Heterogeneous Compute Utilization*: Our framework supports ML execution on CPUs, GPUs, and microcontrollers, enabling adaptive offloading based on workload demands and resource availability.

By evaluating simple ML inference workloads across a range of devices - including ESP32, Raspberry Pi 5, Jetson AGX, and x86 cloud servers - we demonstrate that MLIoT can potentially reduce inference latency and improve execution efficiency while maintaining security guarantees.

In this work, we identify limitations in current approaches for ML inference in IoT/Edge infrastructure, both in terms of firmware management as well as application development and deployment. Additionally, we introduce a secure device onboarding and Over-The-Air (OTA) update framework using DICE and EATs to ensure trusted execution environments, even on devices with limited hardware capabilities. Finally, we evaluate ML inference performance on various heterogeneous devices, showing that the cost of offloading computation to neighboring nodes via vAccel is beneficial.

II. BACKGROUND & MOTIVATION

A. ML Offloading in IoT and Robotics

The advent of IoT and robotics has significantly expanded the use cases of ML in a variety of real-time applications. These applications, ranging from autonomous navigation (e.g.,

for UAVs and robotic vehicles) to predictive maintenance in industrial settings, rely heavily on real-time decision-making using complex sensor data. Many of these applications demand that ML models, such as DNNs or decision trees, be deployed on devices with severe resource constraints, such as low-power microcontrollers or edge devices [9].

Running deep learning models locally on such constrained devices is a challenging task, often resulting in high inference latency and increased power consumption. Moreover, the resource limitations - both in terms of processing power and memory - make it difficult for these devices to execute sophisticated models in real-time, particularly for large models requiring significant computational power. While cloud-based processing offers higher computational capabilities, sending large amounts of sensor data to the cloud for ML inference introduces significant latency and bandwidth usage, making it impractical in scenarios where low-latency processing is required. Additionally, the reliance on continuous network connectivity for cloud-based inference poses a problem in environments with intermittent or unreliable network connections, such as remote areas or during mobile operations. Finally, applications need to be adapted to offload computation to Cloud or Edge nodes, introducing additional overhead to the application developer, as well as the provider that needs to adapt, configure and deploy the application accordingly.

To overcome these challenges, it is increasingly important to enable local data processing [10] and minimize data transport to the cloud or edge servers. By performing ML inference on local devices (e.g., IoT devices or edge nodes), we can significantly reduce the amount of data that needs to be transmitted, thereby minimizing bandwidth usage. This local processing approach ensures that only essential data or results are sent to the cloud, allowing for more efficient use of network resources and mitigating the impact of unreliable networks.

At the same time, offloading computationally intensive ML tasks to more powerful edge or cloud devices can still provide the benefits of higher performance while maintaining local control over critical decisions. The key challenge lies in developing *dynamic offloading strategies* that allow devices to determine whether to execute computations locally or offload them, based on real-time conditions such as device capabilities, network availability, latency requirements, and power consumption constraints. This flexibility enables systems to adapt to varying network conditions and optimize data flow within the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, while relieving the application developer and the service provider from complicated setups.

B. Secure Device Onboarding and Firmware Management

In the context of distributed ML inference, security becomes a critical concern [11], especially when IoT devices interact with more powerful edge or cloud resources. Many IoT devices lack the necessary hardware and software mechanisms to authenticate themselves securely in the cloud or edge infrastructure. Moreover, the process of updating device firmware - particularly in remote or large-scale deployments -

poses significant challenges [12]. OTA updates are essential for keeping device firmware up to date, but they must be executed in a secure and trusted manner to prevent malicious interference. Additionally, many IoT devices are deployed with fixed, single-purpose workloads, yet advances in lightweight AI models and cloud-native orchestration enable dynamic adaptation to new tasks [13]. Repurposing devices for AI inference, federated learning, or real-time analytics reduces e-waste, lowers costs, and enhances system resilience.

One approach to ensuring secure device onboarding and trustworthy firmware updates is through the use of DICE and EATs. DICE provides a framework for generating secure, cryptographically verifiable device identities during the device boot process. This identity can then be used for remote attestation, ensuring that the device’s firmware and runtime environment have not been tampered with. EATs, on the other hand, provide a standardized format for attesting the state of the device and ensuring that the device’s software integrity is maintained. When applied to IoT devices, DICE and EATs help guarantee that devices can authentically claim their identity and remain trustworthy when they interact with the cloud, edge servers, or other devices in the continuum.

This security foundation is vital for the successful deployment of distributed systems where IoT devices must perform remote computations on edge or cloud resources, and where those computations need to be kept secure and reliable.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF KEY CHALLENGES AND CORRESPONDING MLIOT SOLUTIONS.

Challenge	MLIoT Approach
Secure onboarding and OTA firmware	DICE-based device identity + EATs for runtime integrity
IoT-cloud orchestration gap	Cloud-native integration with Kubernetes
Dynamic ML inference placement	Runtime decision engine in vAccel based on latency, power, and bandwidth
Resource heterogeneity (CPU/GPU/MCU)	Unified vAccel API and pluggable hardware backend support

C. vAccel: Transparent ML Offloading

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the vAccel offloading framework.

Existing frameworks for offloading ML workloads often focus on specific application scenarios. These solutions typically require explicit *application-level* modifications or *hardware-specific accelerators* (such as GPUs, TPUs, or FPGAs) to

offload computations. However, such approaches are often rigid and inefficient, especially when devices must interact with heterogeneous computing environments, which may include different hardware architectures (CPUs, GPUs, edge accelerators) or cloud-based services.

To address these limitations, we leverage vAccel¹ [8], a cloud-native, transparent offloading framework that abstracts the complexity of workload distribution across heterogeneous devices. vAccel provides a unified API for offloading ML inference tasks, allowing applications to execute models on devices with higher computational capabilities without having to modify application code or understand the underlying hardware. The framework enables API remoting, which means that an IoT device can delegate ML tasks to a more capable edge or cloud resource based on the device’s current workload, power budget, and latency constraints, without application-level modifications. By integrating vAccel to IoT applications, we enable dynamic offloading, where the decision of whether to run the model locally on the IoT device or offload it to another node (e.g., an edge server or a cloud instance) is made based on runtime conditions.

Additionally, vAccel ensures security and isolation by executing offloaded computations within sandboxed environments, providing a layer of protection against potential attacks. It also allows for multi-backend support, where ML inference tasks can be executed not only on CPUs but also on GPUs, TPUs, and specialized accelerators, further optimizing performance.

D. Comparison with Existing Offloading Frameworks

To highlight the unique contributions of the MLIoT framework, Table II compares our system against several representative ML offloading and orchestration solutions, including Edge Impulse [14], TensorFlow Lite RPC [15], TVM RPC [16], AWS Greengrass [17], and Azure IoT Edge [18]. We evaluate each system across four dimensions: (i) supported hardware classes, (ii) integrated security mechanisms, (iii) runtime adaptivity, and (iv) support for cloud-native orchestration.

While commercial platforms such as Greengrass and Azure IoT Edge support containerized deployments and secure communication, they generally do not target microcontrollers or support lightweight OTA firmware delivery. Open-source offloading tools like TFLite RPC or TVM RPC offer backend acceleration but require manual setup and lack orchestration capabilities. In contrast, MLIoT provides a unified solution that spans constrained devices to cloud backends, combining dynamic offloading, secure onboarding using DICE and EATs, and Kubernetes-native orchestration for deployment at scale.

Positioning Relative to Greengrass and Azure IoT Edge: While commercial platforms like AWS Greengrass [17] and Azure IoT Edge [18] offer tight integration with their respective cloud ecosystems and support basic ML offloading workflows, they typically assume capable edge hardware and rely on proprietary onboarding and attestation methods, such

as TPMs. This limits their use in deployments involving ultra-constrained microcontrollers. In contrast, MLIoT explicitly targets such constrained devices and builds on open standards for secure onboarding, namely DICE and EATs.

Other frameworks such as Edge Impulse [14], TensorFlow Lite RPC [15], and TVM RPC [16] focus primarily on static inference deployment and often lack support for runtime adaptivity or cloud-native orchestration. These systems also do not support dynamic workload migration across heterogeneous hardware or secure firmware delivery using standard tooling (e.g., OCI containers). In contrast, MLIoT’s use of the vAccel runtime allows for adaptive inference routing, while its integration with Kubernetes and custom CRDs enables seamless orchestration and device repurposing at scale.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN & ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we describe the system architecture and design decisions made to enable secure, efficient, and scalable ML inference offloading within the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. Our design aims to address the unique challenges posed by resource-constrained devices, heterogeneous computing environments, and the need for minimal data transport to the cloud, especially in low-bandwidth or intermittently connected settings. We present a cloud-native framework that enables IoT devices to dynamically offload computation to more powerful neighboring nodes, ensuring that computation is performed efficiently while minimizing the use of network resources.

A. Overview

The architecture is based on three key components:

a) IoT Devices (Edge Nodes): These devices are typically resource-constrained (e.g., ESP32 microcontrollers, low-end Raspberry Pi devices, with 4GB of RAM or less) and are responsible for collecting sensor data and executing lightweight ML inference tasks. They can also act as the initial point of interaction for ML workloads but are limited in their computational capabilities.

b) Edge Servers: These more powerful devices, such as high-end Raspberry Pi devices (eg with 8GB of RAM), NVIDIA Jetson, or other edge computing platforms, have increased processing power and memory, making them more capable of running complex ML models. Edge servers serve as intermediaries for offloading computation from the IoT devices. They can process ML inference tasks locally, reducing the need to send data to the cloud.

c) Cloud Infrastructure: The cloud infrastructure provides the most powerful computational resources, offering virtually unlimited scalability for ML inference workloads. It is used for back-end processing or for handling highly computationally intensive tasks that cannot be handled by edge servers or IoT devices. However, cloud interaction is minimized to avoid excessive latency and bandwidth costs, especially when local resources are sufficient for handling the workload.

The goal of the system is to create a seamless handover of computational tasks between these components, based on

¹<https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel>

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF MLIOT WITH EXISTING ML OFFLOADING FRAMEWORKS.

Framework	HW Support	Security Mechanisms	Adaptive Runtime	Cloud-Native
MLIoT	MCU, CPU, GPU, FPGA, etc.	DICE, EATs, TLS	✓(vAccel)	✓(K8s, OCI)
Edge Impulse	MCU, CPU	Basic TLS	✗	Partial
TF Lite RPC	CPU, GPU	TLS (manual)	✗	✗
TVM RPC	CPU, GPU, FPGA	TLS (manual)	Partial	✗
AWS Greengrass	CPU, GPU	IAM + TLS	Partial	Partial
Azure IoT Edge	CPU, GPU	TPM + TLS	Partial	Partial

real-time device status, network conditions, and workload characteristics. By doing so, we can ensure that data remains local to the devices when possible and only sent to the cloud when necessary. This transparent offloading is achieved through the vAccel framework, which abstracts the complexity of distributing ML inference tasks across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum.

B. Data Minimization and Local Processing

One of the main design objectives is to reduce the amount of data that must be transmitted to the cloud, thereby minimizing bandwidth usage and reducing the impact of network interruptions. To achieve this, we adopt a local-first processing model where as much computation as possible is handled on the IoT device or on nearby edge nodes, before considering cloud offloading.

In practice, IoT devices are designed to perform initial data processing and basic ML inference tasks locally. These devices collect data from sensors (e.g., cameras, LIDAR, temperature sensors) and perform pre-processing (e.g., filtering, feature extraction) before sending the processed data or results to more powerful devices for further analysis. In many cases, only aggregated or high-level results (such as classification labels, anomaly detection results, or summarized sensor readings) are transmitted to the cloud, reducing data transfer volume.

When the local device reaches its computational limits, or when low-latency inference is not possible, the system dynamically decides whether to offload the workload to an edge server or the cloud. This decision is made based on a combination of factors such as:

- *Real-time response requirements*: Critical tasks that require immediate results are processed locally or offloaded to the nearest edge node for fast responses.
- *Power budgets*: Devices with strict energy constraints will prioritize local processing or offloading to lower-power edge devices.
- *Network conditions*: If the network connection is unreliable or the bandwidth is constrained, the system prioritizes local processing to avoid sending large amounts of data over the network. In the case of intermittent network connectivity, computation can continue locally, and the device can asynchronously offload results when the network becomes available.

C. Offloading Strategy with vAccel

vAccel, our cloud-native offloading framework, enables transparent and flexible offloading of ML inference tasks

across the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. By abstracting the complexities of offloading across heterogeneous devices, vAccel allows the system to automatically route ML workloads to the most appropriate computational resources based on current device and network conditions.

The vAccel framework provides a uniform API for offloading tasks, making it possible for IoT devices to delegate ML computations to edge devices or the cloud without modifying their codebase. The framework, through a simplistic and flexible plugin system, supports heterogeneous hardware, including CPUs, GPUs, and specialized accelerators like FPGAs, ensuring that the system can utilize the most suitable hardware for each task.

When local resources are insufficient, the system evaluates the network conditions (e.g., latency, bandwidth) and the computational requirements of the workload to determine whether to offload to an edge node or the cloud. In the case of low bandwidth or intermittent connectivity, offloading can be deferred or re-routed to an edge device with a stable network connection.

The secure offloading process is also a key consideration of the vAccel framework. Devices ensure that the computational tasks remain secure by using TEEs for offloaded workloads. Additionally, the system ensures that minimal sensitive data is transmitted to the cloud, using secure protocols such as TLS/SSL to safeguard data in transit.

D. Device and Resource Orchestration

A major challenge in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum is ensuring efficient resource utilization across the diverse set of devices involved. This requires dynamic orchestration of devices based on device capabilities, workload characteristics, and current system states. The system orchestrates the placement of workloads across IoT devices, edge servers, and cloud resources based on available computational power, network conditions, and real-time latency requirements.

In this context, Kubernetes and containerized workloads play a vital role in resource orchestration, especially for managing edge and cloud nodes that execute offloaded tasks. Custom controllers and Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) are used to ensure that devices running the vAccel agent are properly managed and that workloads are assigned to the most suitable device based on the current network and device capabilities. Kubernetes helps in maintaining high availability of computational resources and ensures seamless scaling of workloads as more devices are added to the network [19].

E. Execution Flow

Fig. 2. Offloading ML inference tasks to neighboring nodes via the vAccel framework

Figure 2 presents the steps of a typical offloading scenario. The execution flow consists of the following steps:

- **Model Execution Request:** The IoT device requests ML inference.
- **vAccel Decision Engine:** Determines whether local execution is feasible or offloading is required.
- **Workload Offloading:** If offloading is selected, the operation is forwarded to an appropriate accelerator node (e.g., Jetson GPU, x86).
- **Secure Execution & Response:** The result is computed and sent back securely.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

This section details the key components and technologies implemented in the proposed framework for ML inference offloading across the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. The implementation focuses on integrating the vAccel framework, secure device onboarding with DICE and EATs, and local data processing for efficient ML offloading. We also describe the Kubernetes-based orchestration and the deployment pipeline for these components.

A. Hardware Setup

The system was tested on a diverse set of hardware platforms to evaluate the performance of ML inference offloading in various configurations. The devices used include:

IoT Devices (ESP32): These low-power microcontrollers are used to represent resource-constrained IoT devices. They are capable of handling basic sensor data collection and preprocessing tasks but have limited computational power. For ML inference tasks, they can perform basic computations, but for more complex tasks, we offload workloads to neighboring edge devices or the cloud.

Edge Devices (Raspberry Pi 5, NVIDIA Jetson AGX): These devices serve as the intermediary between the IoT devices and the cloud. The Raspberry Pi 5 provides a low-cost yet capable solution for edge processing, while the Jetson AGX offers higher computational resources, particularly useful for tasks requiring GPU acceleration, such as deep learning inference.

Cloud Servers (x86-based): For tasks that require substantial computational resources (e.g., large-scale ML models or data aggregation across devices), cloud servers are used. These servers are equipped with multi-core CPUs and GPUs, offering significant computational capacity to handle more complex ML workloads.

Each ESP32 device embeds a DICE-based boot sequence that derives a cryptographic identity during secure boot. This identity is used to generate EAT tokens, which are included in each offloading request. Edge/Cloud servers verify these tokens before accepting inference tasks, ensuring provenance and integrity of incoming requests.

B. Software frameworks

To implement the framework for offloading ML inference, the following software tools and technologies were used:

vAccel Framework: As the backbone of the offloading process, vAccel abstracts away the complexities of cross-platform computation, enabling transparent task offloading across IoT, edge, and cloud devices. The framework provides an API for remote execution, allowing devices to offload ML inference tasks to neighboring nodes, either in the edge or cloud. vAccel supports the use of diverse hardware accelerators, including CPUs and GPUs, and abstracts the underlying hardware differences from the application.

The implementation of vAccel relies on a custom API remoting layer that interfaces with the hardware and manages the execution of inference tasks. The vAccel client running on IoT devices communicates with the vAccel agent on the target device (either an edge server or cloud node) to offload tasks based on real-time resource and network conditions.

Kubernetes Orchestration: To ensure efficient distribution of resources and workload management, the framework uses Kubernetes as the container orchestration platform. Kubernetes is configured to manage the deployment of edge and cloud workloads, ensuring that ML inference tasks are scheduled based on resource availability and device capability.

Akri² is a CNCF open-source project that extends k8s by enabling the *discovery*, *inventory management*, and *utilization* of IoT devices. It extends k8s' resource interface and enables **dynamic** device discovery and usage. Akri is essentially a k8s Controller alongside an Agent that sits on each cluster node, polling for IoT devices using a *fully customizable* discovery interface. *BrokerPods* accompany Akri instances to facilitate communication with the external world.

We build on this framework, and extend it using custom CRDs and a custom controller, to ensure that vAccel-enabled devices can be properly registered, monitored, and dynamically allocated based on system demands. Additionally, the controller enables seamless communication between the Kubernetes control plane and the vAccel agent, allowing for efficient orchestration of workloads across highly heterogeneous platforms. Figure 3 presents the participating components for IoT device repurposing in the context of Akri and our own custom controller.

²<https://docs.akri.sh>

Fig. 3. High-level view of IoT device repurposing and orchestration from the perspective of the orchestrator

To facilitate software delivery and align the framework to the Cloud-native ecosystem, we package firmware blobs as *OCI artifacts*, which can be stored in any OCI-compliant registry. These artifacts are designed to support *multiple* devices and configurations, minimizing the burden of managing the deployment of a single application across diverse hardware. Figure 4 visualizes a simple pipeline that, given the source

Fig. 4. Workflow for packaging and distributing ESP32 firmware as OCI-compliant artifacts.

code of an application ported to an IoT device framework (such as ESP32-based devices, with `esp-idf`), *builds* the binary blob, *packages* it as an OCI image and *creates* an image manifest, annotating each OCI image with metadata. These images and manifests are pushed to a generic container registry and can be retrieved using generic container tooling.

DICE and EATs for Secure Device Onboarding: For secure interactions between IoT devices and edge or cloud nodes, the DICE framework was implemented to ensure device authentication and trusted execution. Using DICE-based identifiers, devices are able to prove their authenticity and ensure that the remote nodes they interact with are trusted. Figure 5 presents the sequence diagram of a device repurposing scenario.

In addition, EATs are used to provide cryptographic evidence of the integrity of both the IoT devices and the edge/cloud servers they communicate with. This ensures that the remote devices can verify the integrity of the offloading tasks and ensure that they are not tampered with.

Fig. 5. Sequence diagram illustrating secure onboarding and repurposing of IoT devices using DICE and EATs

C. Offloading and Task Scheduling

The offloading process is dynamic and context-aware, with tasks being offloaded based on factors such as:

- **Compute Capacity:** If an IoT or edge device does not have sufficient resources (e.g., CPU or memory) to process an ML task within the required time, the task is offloaded to a neighboring device with more resources. The decision-making process is managed by the vAccel components, which dynamically evaluate the capabilities of the available devices in real-time.
- **Network Conditions:** The system uses a network monitoring module to determine the stability and bandwidth availability of the network. If the network is stable and has sufficient bandwidth, offloading to the cloud can occur. However, in cases of low or intermittent connectivity, the system prefers offloading to nearby edge devices, thus ensuring that tasks can still be processed even if the connection to the cloud is temporarily unavailable.
- **Latency and Real-Time Constraints:** Tasks that require real-time processing (e.g., autonomous navigation or real-time sensor fusion) are prioritized for local execution or offloading to nearby edge devices. The system uses a latency-aware scheduling mechanism to ensure that time-sensitive tasks are handled within the specified deadlines.

D. Device Management and Secure Over-the-Air Updates

Secure device onboarding and secure OTA updates are implemented using DICE and EATs. The process of updating device firmware securely is crucial for maintaining the integrity and security of the IoT devices in the continuum.

- **OTA Updates:** The framework supports secure OTA updates, ensuring that only trusted firmware updates are applied to devices, while also ensuring updates occur on trusted devices. Using DICE, devices are authenticated with the rest of the infrastructure, while EATs provide assurances that the firmware has not been tampered with. This ensures that IoT devices can be remotely updated without compromising security or reliability.

- *Device Health Monitoring*: The system continuously monitors the health and status of all devices in the continuum, ensuring that devices are operating correctly and securely. Any device exhibiting irregular behavior, such as compromised integrity or security vulnerabilities, is flagged for immediate intervention, preventing potential threats from spreading throughout the system.

E. Security Considerations

In addition to using DICE and EATs for secure device onboarding and OTA updates, the system incorporates end-to-end encryption for data transmitted between devices. The use of TLS/SSL protocols ensures that all communications are securely encrypted, preventing data interception or tampering during the offloading process. Furthermore, the authorization and authentication mechanisms ensure that only trusted devices can participate in the offloading process, protecting the system from unauthorized access.

F. Monitoring and Performance Evaluation

The system also includes a monitoring layer that tracks the performance of offloaded tasks and evaluates the effectiveness of offloading decisions. Metrics such as latency, resource utilization, and power consumption are continuously monitored to assess the system’s efficiency. Additionally, performance dashboards were implemented for administrators to visualize device health, task status, and resource allocation across the entire continuum.

V. EVALUATION

To assess the performance of ML inference across heterogeneous devices, we evaluate four models trained on the *Fashion MNIST* dataset [20]: Simple CNN, ResNet8, ResNet10 (with int8 quantization), and Tiny MobileNet (with int8 quantization). The inference was tested on four distinct hardware classes:

- Cloud CPUs: Intel Core i7-8565U, AMD Ryzen 5 2600
- Cloud GPUs: NVIDIA RTX 2060 SUPER
- Edge Devices: Raspberry Pi 5 Model B (ARM Cortex-A76)
- Constrained IoT Devices: ESP32-S3-DevKitC-1U-N8R2

We evaluate the following metrics:

- Inference time (ms): Average latency per forward pass.
- Standard deviation: Variability in inference time.
- Accuracy (%): Model classification performance.

A. Accuracy Across Devices

Across all tested models, classification accuracy remains relatively stable, with minor variations due to different optimizations and quantization techniques. Notably, ResNet10 (int8 quantized) achieves the highest accuracy of 94.5% on x86 CPUs, while Tiny MobileNet reached 93% on the same platform. The ESP32-S3 shows a minor drop in accuracy (e.g., 93.6% for ResNet10), likely due to quantization effects and limited computational precision.

B. Inference Latency Across Platforms

1) *Performance on Cloud and Edge CPUs*: Inference on x86 processors demonstrated predictable performance, with Intel Core i7-8565U consistently outperforming AMD Ryzen 5 2600. For example, ResNet10 inference on the Intel CPU averaged 12.53 ms, while the same model on the AMD CPU required 15.69 ms.

On Raspberry Pi 5, inference times were 2-4× slower compared to x86 CPUs, indicating the limitations of ARM-based compute for deep learning.

2) *Performance on Cloud GPUs*: The NVIDIA RTX 2060 SUPER provided the lowest inference latencies, demonstrating up to a 10× speedup over CPU-based inference. For example, Tiny MobileNet inference on the RTX 2060 completed in 0.92 ms, compared to 3.79 ms on an Intel Core i7-8565U and 4.13 ms on an AMD Ryzen 5 2600.

3) *Performance on ESP32*: Inference on the ESP32-S3-DevKitC-1U-N8R2 revealed extreme latency overheads, particularly for complex models. ResNet10 model required 13.4 seconds (13397 ms) to complete a single inference pass, making real-time processing infeasible. Even the simpler Tiny MobileNet model required 624 ms, an order of magnitude slower than Raspberry Pi 5 (1.9 ms).

Fig. 6. Inference latency across models and platforms (logarithmic scale).

Fig. 7. Classification accuracy across platforms for various ML models.

These results underscore the importance of offloading ML inference to more powerful devices within the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. Despite the network overhead associated with transmitting inference data to edge nodes and retrieving the results, the benefits of offloading still outweigh the costs.

C. Memory Footprint on ESP32

Deploying ML models on ESP32-class microcontrollers is constrained by limited RAM and Flash memory. Table III shows the footprint of each model:

TABLE III
FLASH AND RAM REQUIREMENTS FOR DIFFERENT ML MODELS ON THE ESP32.

Model	Flash Storage (KB)	RAM Usage (KB)
Simple CNN	36 KB	32 KB
ResNet8	92 KB	152 KB
ResNet10 (int8 quant)	700 KB	334 KB
Tiny MobileNet (int8 quant)	1.2 MB	302 KB

The results indicate that even small-scale models require careful optimization. Tiny Mobilenet consumes over 1 MB of flash storage, which exceeds the memory limits of many IoT microcontrollers. In contrast, Resnet10 provides a more memory-efficient alternative, balancing accuracy and resource constraints.

D. Implications for ML Inference Offloading

These results reinforce the argument for offloading ML inference workloads to more capable devices. Given that:

- ESP32 inference is prohibitively slow (e.g., 13.4s for ResNet10), real-time execution is impractical.
- Edge devices (Raspberry Pi 5) are 5-10× faster than ESP32, but still lag behind dedicated AI accelerators.
- Cloud GPUs are orders of magnitude faster, but introduce network overheads when offloading from edge or IoT devices.

Thus, the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum provides an optimal trade-off, where models can be dynamically deployed based on:

- Latency constraints (offload to nearest available edge node).
- Power budgets (minimize network transmission for battery-powered devices).
- Accuracy requirements (leverage cloud GPUs for high-precision inference).

Taken together, these results validate MLIoT’s design choices. While network latency introduces some overhead, it is expected to be overshadowed by the dramatic reduction in local inference times. This suggests that for many robotics and time-sensitive IoT applications, offloading is not only practical but essential.

VI. DISCUSSION & FUTURE WORK

A. Benefits of Offloading in the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum for Robotics

In the context of robotics, the ability to offload ML inference tasks across the continuum of IoT, edge, and cloud devices

provides a transformative opportunity for the development of autonomous systems and collaborative robotics. Robotics, especially in applications like autonomous navigation, object recognition, sensor fusion, and path planning, often rely on computationally intensive algorithms that require real-time processing [21]. IoT devices like robots and UAVs are often constrained by limited computational resources, battery life, and power budgets, making it challenging to run these algorithms locally [22].

Offloading computational tasks to more capable edge devices or the cloud helps mitigate these limitations [23]. For example, a robot equipped with a resource-constrained IoT device (like an ESP32) can offload tasks like SLAM or deep learning-based image classification to a nearby edge node like a Jetson AGX, which is capable of performing the required computations efficiently [24]. Offloading also enables the parallelization of computationally intensive tasks, where multiple robots or drones can share resources, further optimizing task execution and system efficiency [25].

One of the most significant advantages in the robotics domain is the reduced latency for real-time decision-making. In autonomous systems, even small delays can result in failures, like navigating into obstacles or failing to meet real-time task deadlines [26]. By processing data and making decisions at the edge or nearby nodes, the system avoids the delays associated with sending data to a remote cloud server, enabling faster, safer, and more efficient operations [27]. This is critical for applications such as robotic surgery, autonomous delivery, and warehouse automation, where decision-making needs to occur in real-time.

Moreover, network stability is paramount, particularly when robots are deployed in environments where network conditions are unreliable [28]. By using the edge as a local offloading destination, our system minimizes the reliance on intermittent cloud connectivity, thus making robots more resilient in environments with poor network coverage, such as in remote industrial facilities or in disaster response scenarios [29].

B. Trade-Offs and Challenges for Robotics Applications

While the offloading strategy provides numerous benefits to robotic systems, several challenges specific to robotics need to be addressed:

Computational Complexity: Robotic systems often rely on complex multi-modal sensor data, such as LIDAR, RGBD cameras, and IMUs, to perceive and interact with their environment. These data streams can be computationally expensive to process, and offloading them to neighboring edge devices can lead to network bottlenecks if the data volumes are too high [30]. For example, processing large-scale LIDAR scans for autonomous vehicle navigation may require significant computational power. A balance must be found between local processing and offloading, based on the computational needs of the task and the current network conditions.

Autonomy and Offline Operation: A core principle of robotics is ensuring that systems can operate autonomously in environments where cloud or edge connectivity may be

intermittent or unavailable [31]. In such scenarios, it is essential to ensure that the robot can continue performing essential tasks locally, even if offloading is temporarily not an option. Future work could focus on integrating more advanced fault-tolerance mechanisms that allow the robot to fall back on local computation without compromising its decision-making abilities.

Coordinating Collaborative Robotics: In multi-robot systems, collaborative tasks (such as formation control or swarms) introduce additional challenges for offloading. In such environments, the system must manage not only individual offloading but also coordinate task sharing and resource allocation across multiple devices [32]. This introduces complexity in terms of resource contention between robots, requiring advanced scheduling algorithms [33] that can dynamically allocate computational tasks across all available nodes to avoid conflicts and inefficiencies.

C. Implications for Robotics and Future Work

Looking ahead, the integration of ML inference offloading in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum holds immense potential for robotics. One promising direction is to explore how autonomous robots can use cloud-edge hybrid architectures to leverage real-time data synchronization and collaborative multi-robot systems [34]. For example, in smart warehouses or autonomous fleets, robots could work in tandem, with each robot offloading specific tasks to different edge nodes, allowing the system to meet real-time operational goals without overburdening any individual robot.

Additionally, incorporating AI-driven coordination between robots and centralized cloud servers could lead to more intelligent task distribution, improving efficiency in complex environments [35]. By using reinforcement learning or game-theoretic models, robots could dynamically adjust their offloading decisions based on the local and global context, improving system-wide performance and robustness.

Lastly, the security of robotic systems is paramount, especially when they interact with humans or handle sensitive tasks. In our framework, the secure onboarding and OTA updates using DICE and EATs provide a strong foundation for ensuring that robots can operate safely and securely within the continuum. Future work should investigate more advanced privacy-preserving techniques for collaborative robots to protect sensitive data when performing joint tasks, such as decentralized privacy-preserving ML models for collaborative robotics [36].

D. Conclusion

This paper presents the motivation for a novel framework that enables ML inference task offloading across the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. We demonstrate that the ability to offload computationally intensive tasks to neighboring edge devices or the cloud allows resource-constrained IoT devices, such as robots, to perform real-time decision-making with lower latency, reduced power consumption, and more efficient resource utilization.

For robotic systems, especially those in autonomous navigation, collaborative robotics, and industrial automation, our framework enables robots to overcome the limitations of local processing by dynamically offloading tasks based on computational capacity, network conditions, and real-time operational constraints. Leveraging edge computing and heterogeneous resources, the system enhances the performance and scalability of such systems, paving the way for more intelligent and collaborative robots in the future.

Despite the promising results, challenges remain, particularly in terms of resource contention, multi-robot coordination, and network stability. Further research is needed to refine the task scheduling mechanisms and fault tolerance strategies that allow robots to perform their tasks seamlessly, even in dynamic and uncertain environments. Additionally, exploring privacy-preserving and secure collaborative systems for robots will be crucial as more robots are deployed in sensitive domains.

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